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THE PRAGMATICS OF CAMEROON ENGLISH

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to demonstrate that the meaning of a number of speech acts in Cameroon English (CamE) cannot be got from the linguistic elements used but from the context of use. The data are analysed using the speech act theory as propounded by Austin (1962) and defended by pragmaticians such as Searle (1969), Mey (1993), and Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan (2010). Using the above theory, a number of speech acts were collected from the day to day interactions of Cameroonians between 2020 and 2023 and were analysed following their locutionary aspects, their illocutionary effects, and their perlocutionary force. The analysis shows that as the years go by, English speaking Cameroonians become even more and more creative in the way they construct and use their utterances. The meaning of these utterances is never dependent on the surface meaning of the wordings used but on the shared contextual knowledge of both the speaker and the audience. For example, in the sentence "has Fame Ndongo spoken to you?", one might be tempted to think that the Cameroonian Minister of higher education (at least by the time this article was being written) had to talk to someone. Interestingly, this has nothing to do with someone speaking (verbally) to another. Rather, from the context of university lecturers in Cameroon, it is about the payment of research allowance by the government. The findings of the study therefore intimate that in order to understand most of the speech acts in CamE, we have to rely more on the intentions of the speaker and the shared contextual knowledge of both the speaker and the listener.

Keywords: Cameroon English, Pragmatics, Speech acts, semantics

1 Introduction

According to Chomsky, language is a natural object, a component of the human mind, physically represented in the brain and part of the biological endowment of the species (Chomsky, 2002). This view of language by Chomsky is in line with other “naturalist” linguists, with Plato as the chief proponent, who see the meaning of words as the entity or thing they represent. Chomsky further sees language as the innate capacity of native speakers to produce grammatically correct sentences. The criticism of this view is that there exist very many words in natural languages without physical entities. That is why Mey (2001), and Martinez-Flor and Usor-Juan (2010:3) posit that the “pragmatic turn”, or the study of language in context is necessary to fill this gap.

There is a clear difference between semantic meaning and pragmatic meaning (discussed in the literature review). While the former deals with “meaning in the abstract”, the latter deals with “meaning in use” (Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan, 2010:3). Now, users of Cameroon English make great use of speech acts whose interpretations and understanding are context based. That is why in an effort to analyse some of these speech acts, this study employs the speech act theory propounded by Austin (1962) and then amplified by the other linguists including Searle (1969), Mey (1993), and Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan (2010).

The work is subdivided as follows: (1) Introduction, (2) Literature Review (3) Methodology, (4) Discussion, and (5) Conclusion. These are taken in turn below.

2 Literature Review

Before reviewing works dealing with speech acts, the following notions will be examined: Cameroon English, semantics and pragmatics, the speech act theory.

Simo Bobda and Mbangwana (1993) posit that the term *Cameroon English* or *Cameroon Standard English* is meant to contrast with four main kinds of speech. First, it stands in contrast to Pidgin English widely used in Cameroon. Second, it contrasts with the speech of the uneducated speakers of English. That is why it is often synonymous with educated English. Cameroon English (CamE), according to the above scholars, is situated between the speech of secondary school leavers and that of university graduates. It further

contrasts with the speech of Francophone Cameroonians; some of these speakers may have a high command of English, but they are regarded as users of a performance variety and can hardly serve as a reference. Furthermore, the term *Cameroon English* excludes the speech of a handful of Cameroonians who have been so influenced by other varieties (Standard British English, American English, etc.) that they can no longer be considered representative of the English spoken in Cameroon.

This monolithic approach of considering English in Cameroon as a variety of its own has been propagated by various researchers over the years. For example, Kouega (2007) says, "Cameroon is a Central African country whose variety of English shares a number of features with West African Englishes". This is in line with what Quirk et al.'s (1972) model considers as an EFL variety and what Kachru's (1985) WE paradigm considers as an Outer Circle new English.

However, Ngefac (2022) argues that there are several Englishes in Cameroon and not just a single variety. In this publication, he states:

The nomenclature "Cameroon English" blurs and conceals the exact sociolinguistic statuses of English in Cameroon, considering that it excludes Cameroon Francophone English, considered in the context of Quirk et al.'s model as EFL and in the context of Kachru's WE paradigm as an Expanding Circle English or a performance variety. Furthermore, the appellation "Cameroon English", considered in the contexts of previous models as an ESL or an Outer Circle English, excludes an L1 status the language is fast acquiring in Cameroon as a result of the fact that there is an alarming increase of native speakers, as reported in Ngefac (this volume)¹. Finally, Cameroon English excludes Cameroon Creole English (Ngefac, 2016) or what is also referred to as Cameroon Pidgin English or Kamtok. With regard to this language, there is a school of thought that thinks that it is in a dialectal continuum with English (e.g. Sala, 2009), but there is another school of thought that considers it a separate language with a distinct linguistic system (see Ngefac and Todd, 2014 and Ngefac, 2016). Whatever the case, what current World Englishes theorizing considers as Cameroon English is just one of the Englishes spoken in this postcolonial multilingual nation (Ngefac, 2022).

The present work, however, adopts Quirk et al.'s (1972) model that would rather consider CamE as an EFL/ESL variety and Kachru's (1985) Outer Circle new Englishes paradigm, all cited in Ngefac (2022). This is for the simple reason that, though several factors have made it possible for new Englishes to emerge in Cameroon (Ngefac, 2022), they unavoidably share a lot in common given their proximity and cohabitation.

As far as semantics and pragmatics is concerned, semantics focuses on the conventional meaning of linguistic items (words, phrases, and sentences) as prescribed in the dictionary (Yule 1996 and Cutting 2002) and explores how these linguistic items "literally connect to things" (Yule 1996), according to their pure linguistic meanings (Peccei 1999).

In other words, semantics is concerned with the general and objective meaning, which does not depend on what speakers intend to convey and how hearers interpret and understand what is said.

Unlike semantics which is concerned with “meaning in the abstract” (Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan 2010), pragmatics focuses on “meaning in use” (Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan 2010) or on the context-specific meaning that emerges when language users interact according to a shared knowledge of a given social context. Different linguists have provided diverse definitions of pragmatics, which clearly bring out its defining characteristics. Mey (1995), for instance, considers it as “the science of language seen in relation to its users”. In the same light, Peccei (1999) sees pragmatics as the branch of linguistics that concentrates on those aspects of meaning that cannot be predicted by linguistic knowledge alone and that takes into account knowledge of the physical and social world (Peccei 1999). Like Mey (1995) and Peccei (1999), Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan (2010) consider pragmatics as “the branch of linguistics devoted to examining language use in communication including speakers’ intentions when producing utterances in particular contexts”.

Semantics and Pragmatics are considered sister linguistic branches, yet despite scholarly attempts to dissociate them. Leech (1983) thinks that it is very difficult to make this distinction. He argues as follows:

The view that semantics and pragmatics are distinct, though complementary and interrelated fields of study, is easy to appreciate subjectively, but is more difficult to justify in an objective way (Leech 1983).

According to him, the distinction between semantics and pragmatics can only emerge clearly if a distinction is made between what he calls semanticism, pragmaticism, and complementarism. Semanticism refers to the encroachment of pragmatics into semantics; pragmaticism refers to “semantics inside pragmatics” (Mey 1993), and complementarism is concerned with the fact that both semantics and pragmatics complement each other, in spite of their significant differences. Leech (1983), in other words, maintains that semantics and pragmatics have well defined linguistic boundaries, even though they work in tandem or complement each other significantly in such a way that their differences can sometimes be masked. Whatever the case, pragmatics as a relatively new approach to linguistic inquiry is not only significantly different from its closest linguistic neighbour (semantics), but it is a paradigm shift that markedly departs from the traditional or Chomskyan approach to language study. In fact, Mey (1993) rightly maintains that the semantic component does not “meddle in pragmatic affairs, except when some philosopher forces it to” (Mey 1993). The different definitions of pragmatics proposed by different scholars clearly show what the discipline is and what it is not. In other words, the characteristics of pragmatics are easily discernible from scholars’ attempts to define it. First, “pragmatics is interested in the process of ‘producing’

language and in its 'producers', not just in the end-'product' language" (Mey 2001). It should be noted that the old paradigm of studying language, championed by Chomsky and his followers, treated language as a "human product", focusing more on a native speaker's abstract knowledge or what Chomsky referred to as "competence", but the new paradigm, referred to as pragmatics, rather focuses on language in its human use, focusing on language users and extralinguistic factors, such as the context of use, that interact to determine meaning. In other words, pragmatics is concerned with what Chomsky referred to as "performance", and not "competence", the backbone of Chomskyan linguistics. It is not surprising that Katz (1977), quoted in Mey (2001), says "Grammars are theories about the structure of sentence types ... Pragmatic theories, in contrast ... explicate the reasoning of speakers and hearers". The implication is that pragmatics is concerned with actual linguistic practice or performance, and not with competence or the abstract knowledge of language. Second, pragmatics is not very concerned with users' respect of grammatical norms as they "are doing things in and with language" (Mey, 1993), in spite of the fact that Levinson (1983) maintains that it studies "those relations between language and context that are 'grammaticalised' or encoded in the structure of a language" (Levinson, 1983). The implication of Levinson's view is that users need to respect the grammatical rules of language in order to express pragmatic meaning or meaning that is determined by contextual factors. Levinson (1983), in other words, claims that the respect of the grammatical rules of language is a prerequisite for the speech activities of language users to be pragmatically relevant, thereby claiming that there is an important relationship between pragmatics and grammar. But Mey (1993) rather thinks that [a] truly pragmatic consideration has to deal with the users in their social context; it cannot limit itself to the grammatically encoded aspects of context, as the grammaticalisation requirement seems to imply (Mey, 1993: 6).

The respect of grammatical norms of language is not, therefore, a prerequisite for pragmatics, as Levinson's (1983) grammaticalisation requirement suggests.

Third, pragmatics is not a component of a language theory, but a perspective (Verschueren, 1987 and Mey, 1993). The question of whether pragmatics should be treated as one of the components of the theory of language (phonology, syntax, morphology, and semantics) has been a recurrent issue in some of the previous attempts to define the discipline. Verschueren (1987), quoted in Mey (1993), maintains that pragmatics is a "perspective" that radically departs from the "established component view" and "tries to assign to pragmatics its own set of linguistic features in contradistinction with phonology, morphology, syntax and semantics" (Verschueren 1987 quoted in Mey 1993). Mey (1993) points out that this "perspective" emphasises the pragmatic aspects of the different parts of linguistics. He further maintains that the pragmatic perspective seeks to find how users communicate using the linguistic resources at their disposal.

Fourth, pragmatics depends on the context and the world of language users for a full understanding of utterances. Without a pragmatic consideration or the context and the intentions of the language users, the meaning of utterances is mostly determined by an underlying element known as presupposition. Mey (1993) provides the utterance:

John managed to sell all his shares before the market crashed (to which a bystander remarks, No, he didn't) (Mey 1993).

He points out that some linguists, especially those whose vision is couched in the traditional approach to linguistics, build the survival property of a presupposition “into the very semantics of a particular lexical item” contained in the utterance. He also states that for others, “presuppositions are inextricably tied to a particular lexical item, as when the checker in an American supermarket tells you to ‘Hurry back [to the store]’. Here, the use of the word ‘back’ logically presupposes that you’ve been to the store before: otherwise, you wouldn’t come ‘back’” (Mey 1993).

But without consideration of the context under which a given speech act is enacted and the consideration of the language users’ intentions and interpretations, the full meaning cannot be determined or unveiled. This explains why Mey (1993) maintains that neither a purely logical account, based solely on the truth or falsity of sentences in isolation, nor an exclusively semantic account, based on the value of individual lexical items, will be satisfactory; we must appeal to a pragmatic explanation, based on a particular context of a particular utterer (Mey, 1993).

Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan (2010) summarise the characteristics of pragmatics as follows: (1) the use of language as a means of communication; (2) the importance of language use focusing on functions rather than on forms; (3) the study of processes which occur in communication; (4) the importance of context and authentic language use; (5) the interdisciplinary nature of pragmatics; and (6) the application of linguistic theories based on the notion of communicative competence (Martinez-Flor and Uso-Juan, 2010).

Looking keenly at the characteristics of pragmatics, we notice that the “authentic meaning of linguistic items emerges only when language users perform or enact speech acts in given contexts, based on the realities of that context and their shared knowledge” (Ngefacs, 2021). It further portrays that the language user and the context are the main determinants of meaning, and the conventional meanings of linguistic items play a very little role when language users interact in and with language in real-life situations.

With respect to the Speech Acts Theory, Austin (1962) describes it as an approach that explains the roles of utterances in shaping the attitudes of participants in interpersonal communication while Searle (1969) calls these speech acts the “basic or minimal units of linguistic communication”. Searle (1969) explains this in the following words:

When I take a noise or a mark on a piece of paper to be an instance of linguistic communication, as a message, one of the things I must assume is that the noise or mark was produced by a being or beings more or less like myself and produced with certain kinds of intentions (Searle, 1969).

The implication of speech acts is that every utterance has a purpose which derives from the specific context. It has been observed that language use depends on such contextual factors as social and physical conditions, attitudes, abilities, beliefs and the relationship existing between the speaker and the listener. There are different types of speech acts, the

most common being the following: Representative Acts, Declarative Acts, Directive Acts, Expressive Acts, and Commissive Acts. Representative acts describe events, processes and states. Usually, the speaker is committed to the truth of the assertion, claim, report, suggestion, prediction, description, hypothesis or conclusion. Meanwhile, declarative acts are used in arresting, christening, marriage, sentencing, acquittal, just to name these. These are acts that immediately change the state of affairs to which they apply. Consider the following:

(i) I discharge and acquit the accused

(ii) I hereby name this baby Amanda.

In directive acts, the addressee is instructed to carry out some instruction by responding verbally to an utterance or by performing some physical actions. The acts can be questions, commands, requests, pleas or invitation – e.g.

(i) Kindly lend me some money

(ii) Please, be my guest!

(iii) What is your name!

Expressive acts on their part show the psychological states – feelings and attitudes towards some events and affairs. These usually occur in greetings, scolding, condoling, appreciating, thanking, congratulating, apologising, etc.

(i) We congratulate you on your success.

(ii) I apologise for my mistakes.

Lastly, we have commissive acts, in which the speaker is committed to some future action as in challenging, betting, promising, offering, threatening, vowing, warning, etc.

(i) I pledge a hundred thousand Naira

(ii) We promise to build them a house

It should be noted that commissive acts carry specific performative verbs – promise, swear, name, pledge, warn, advise, declare, bet (Austin, 1962).

Cook (1989) argues that the above acts must be performed by someone who has the necessary authority to do so. For instance a declarative act of pronouncing a man and a woman husband and wife must be spoken (not written) by a clergyman, while sentencing a man to imprisonment should be at the end of a court proceeding by a judge.

Austin (1962) further distinguishes between types of speech acts and levels of speech acts. For levels of speech acts, emphasis is on the different stages of interaction between the speaker and the listener through the use of speech acts. Three distinct levels are usually observed – locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary acts. Locutionary Acts – These are observed as the processes of producing grammatical and meaningful utterances which can be recognised by the hearer. Illocutionary Acts – Illocutionary acts are the force behind the utterances. Indeed, the speaker performs these acts to achieve the purpose of communication as a statement, a question, a command, an invitation, a threat, a request,

an apology etc. It is possible, for instance, to use a sentence that has the structure of a statement for the purpose of a warning. For example, "You will lose all your deposits" – (from a financial adviser to a client). This sentence may be a warning or a piece of advice. Therefore, it is possible to use identical utterance types for different tokens based on the intentions of the speaker and the context. Perlocutionary Acts – These are the effects of the speaker's utterance on the behaviour of the hearer. They are the acts performed by the hearer as a result of the effect of the speaker's utterances. It is assumed, for instance, that the hearer will respond to a question of the speaker in a specific way, or behave in accordance with the demands of the context.

It should be noted that the illocutionary force is the intended effect of an utterance on the hearer from the point of view of the speaker. The perlocutionary effect is the actual effect of the speaker's utterance on the action, behaviour, attitude or belief of the hearer. Maximum communication is achieved when there is illocutionary uptake. This situation arises when the listener understands the intended effect of the speaker. This demand is at the core of semantics since meaning must be shared.

Speech act theory is particularly relevant in this work. This is in line with Ngefac (2021) who says that "certain speech acts performed in Cameroon are analysed in terms of their locutionary aspects, their illocutionary force, and the perlocutionary effects of the acts." He further contends that "it is only in the context of speech act theory that the real meaning of the acts and their correlation with the hearers' reaction can be determined." This implies that the speech act theory provides the perspective from which the pragmatic or the context-specific real-life meanings of the acts can be assessed.

As far as empirical review of literature relating to the pragmatics of Cameroon English is concerned, very little has been done. Ngefac (2021), in an article titled "Beyond Semantics", studied some utterances by Cameroonians. Using the speech act theory propounded by Austin (1962) and defended by Searle (1969), Grice (1975), Leech (1983), and Martinez-Flor and Usor-Juan (2010), he established the fact that a number of speech acts enacted by Cameroonians can only be understood in context and not by the linguistic elements inherent in these acts. He presented the example of a woman who says, "Please, help me to kill that child (shouting)." He explains that here, one can erroneously conclude that the speaker was asking the hearer to actually kill the child, going by the linguistic units involved. He goes ahead to say that analysing the speech act in a socio-cultural context reveals that the speaker's intention was rather to enjoin the hearer to stop beating the child.

Using the same speech act theory propounded by Austin (1962) and then amplified by the other linguists mentioned above, this article pushes further the reflection of speech acts enacted by Cameroonians, especially at a time when Cameroon English (CamE), as a single variety, is moving towards Cameroon Englishes (Ngefac, 2022). This, according to him, is occasioned by factors such as Cameroon Francophone English (CamFE), Cameroon Pidgin English (CPE), the language of urban youth, the language of scammers, just to name these. This present work further departs from that of Ngefac (2021) in that

while Ngefac gathered his data between 2012 and 2016, the data for this work was gathered between 2020 and 2023. It is therefore believed that with the situation of language change over time, the use of speech acts with pragmatic implication will get even more complicated.

3 Methodology

This section focuses primarily on the manner in which the data of the study were collected and analysed, given especially that the methodology used to carry out an investigation of this nature is as important as the findings obtained. The investigation took place in the town of Buea between the years 2020 and 2023. The raw data that were collected comprised utterances from real-life situations of language use by Cameroonians of different walks of life. Each time the investigator witnessed a speech act and the corresponding reaction from the hearer, he would describe it in a notepad. In addition, the investigator would take note of the social context of the interaction, the place where the words were uttered, and the medium through which the acts were performed. The data were analysed following Austin's threefold taxonomy: locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary aspects. In analysing the speech acts, the investigator differentiated the primary meaning from the connotational meaning as understood by the interlocutors.

4 Discussion

Between the years 2020 and 2023, numerous speech acts performed in Cameroon were collected and from that data bank, five of these speech acts have been randomly selected for analysis. As mentioned already, the analysis is done in terms of the locutionary, illocutionary, and perlocutionary aspects, as suggested by Austin's three-fold taxonomy.

Let us begin with the following speech act performed by a university lecturer who is conversing with a fellow colleague.

- (1) My Fame Ndongo is out. (A university lecturer is informing his colleague of the payment into his account of the research modernization allowance.) "What!", the friend exclaims. "I have not yet received a message."

In Cameroon, research modernization allowance is an incentive paid to lecturers of state run universities. It is transferred to the account of each lecturer every quarter of the year. Once this is done, each lecturer is informed by his or her bank through an SMS. Now, Professor Jacques Fame Ndongo is the minister of higher education in Cameroon who has been in that position for close to two decades, and has now become a symbol of that allowance. The exact words uttered by the lecturer – my Fame Ndongo is out – constitute what Austin (1962) refers to as a locutionary act. From the above speech act, a number of questions can be asked. What are the intentions of the lecturer? When he performed that speech act, what did he mean? What did he expect from his fellow colleague? First and foremost, the interlocutors share the same context. They are all university lecturers who usually receive quarterly payments, which are often announced through a ministerial communique. This particular speech act informs the other colleague of the availability of

the research allowance and this kind of illocutionary act is known as “expositive” (Austin, 1962). The exclamation “what!” of the listener gives rise to the perlocutionary aspect of the speech act. We therefore see that the discussion here was never about the person “Fame Ndonga” and whether he is “out” or “in” of the country, for example.

The following is another speech act selected at random for this work.

- (2) Good morning, bros. How far? (A friend meets another in the morning and asks him how he is faring. He answers either by saying “I am fine” or “I am not fine”, depending on his actual situation.

The illocutionary force (intention) of the speech act is that of greetings. Synonymously, the speaker could say, “How are you?” or “how do you do?” Now, the semantic understanding of the word “far” supposes distance. One could therefore easily conclude that if someone asks you “how far”, he or she could be asking you the extent to which you have gone physically (as on a journey) or the extent to which you have carried out a given task (for instance, asking your supervisee how far he or she has gone with his or her research work). But in this speech act we observe that the perlocutionary effect on the listener is that he either says “I am fine” or “I am not fine”. We notice here that the response has nothing to do with distance or extent covered. A peculiarity with this speech act is that inasmuch as it is not Cameroon pidgin English, and in standard British English the second segment “how far” lacks the basic sentence structure (hence, fragment), it is nonetheless a permissible statement in Cameroon English.

The next speech act considered in this work is as follows:

- (3) How was your night? (In the most part, this refers to a girl asking a boy or a boy asking a girl. To a lesser extent, it could simply be one person asking the other).

This seemingly obvious speech act with ordinary linguistic elements such as the question “how was your...” and the vocabulary item “night” has a profound implication. The illocutionary force (intention of the speaker) is that of enquiring whether his or her interlocutor had a good sleep. If it ended there, then an alternative way of putting it could be, “how was your sleep” or “how did you sleep?”. Here, the response would be a simple “fine” or “not fine”. But we observe that, here, the performer of the speech act intends to initiate a discussion, usually emotional in nature, and with the intention of showing that he or she is caring towards the other. That explains why as far as the perlocutionary aspect (effect on the hearer) is concerned, the listener usually feels particularly loved and cared for. With this kind of speech act, the listener is encouraged to open up to his or her interlocutor. Because of the emotional dimension of this speech act, it is quite en vogue among the youth in urban areas, especially within university vicinities.

Another speech act retained for scrutiny is the following:

- (4) I am going to TOTAL. (A member of staff in a given institution told his office colleague. The colleague responded by thanking him and asked him to give him a few minutes to shut down his laptop so they could both go to TOTAL).

This particular speech act was performed in the Buea municipality where the filling station known as TOTAL has a very popular relaxation spot just beside it. Looking at the linguistic elements of the above locution, one is likely to conclude that the speaker intended just to indicate where he was going to. Also, given that TOTAL is a filling station, one could infer that the speaker is informing his or her colleague that he or she is going to the filling station to get some fuel for his or her vehicle. However, an understanding of the utterance in context and the relationship between the interactants show that the illocutionary aspect of the speech act is an invitation for a drink. Instead of the hearer saying something like "ok bros, I am still in the office working", he or she rather thanks the speaker, asking him or her to wait a little so that he or she shuts the computer and they can both go to TOTAL. The above observation is the perlocutionary effect on the hearer who immediately understands that his or her friend is inviting him or her for a drink.

The last speech act to be analysed in this work includes the following:

- (5) Bro, it is bad. I am menstruating already. (A colleague tells another at their place of work on the 20th of the month. The colleague encourages his friend by telling him to persevere, given that it is remaining five days for salaries to be paid to civil servants)

Analysing this speech act out of context is likely to show that the speaker is undoubtedly a woman who is telling the listener (who could be another woman or man) that she is on her monthly period. For her to say "it is bad" before saying that "I am menstruating" may also suggest that her "monthly period" is usually painful or that it has caught her by surprise. However, given that the interactants share knowledge of the fact that towards the end of month, things are usually tough financially with civil servants, it becomes clear that they were talking about financial hardship. The perlocutionary effect of this act on the hearer is seen when the latter encourages the speaker to "persevere given that it is remaining five days for salaries to be paid to civil servants." This, as we can see, has nothing to do with monthly periods and the flow of blood.

5 Conclusion

Aided by the speech act theory propounded by Austin (1962), later on defended and expatiated by other pragmaticians, such as Searle (1969), Mey (1993), and Martinez-Flor and Usor-Juan (2010), the analysis of the selected speech acts performed by Cameroonians demonstrates the fact that to grasp the full meaning of many of the utterances in Cameroon English, one must consider both the context and the relationship that exist between the interlocutors. The fact that Cameron English or Cameroon Standard English (Simo Bobda and Mbangwana (1993) is greatly influenced by Cameroon Pidgin English, as well as the linguistic patterns of many mother tongues further heightens the

metaphorical dimension of most of its speech acts. For instance, saying "...I'm menstruating already" in (5) above, one can quickly conclude that the speaker is experiencing her monthly menstrual flow (passing out blood). But analysing the speech act in context reveals that the speaker intends rather to let his or her interlocutor understand that he or she is already in financial difficulty. This therefore requires that to communicate appropriately within the context of Cameroon English, one should go beyond the semantic implications of the linguistic elements used in the utterance and rather make an effort to discern the speaker's illocutionary aspect and the listener's perlocutionary effect.

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